

The Alan Turing Institute

Data Study Group Final Report: Inmarsat

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Can we use geospatial time-series analyses to predict the demand for a global satellite communications network?

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1 Executive Summary

1.1 Challenge Overview

This report presents the outputs of a week-long collaboration between the Alan Turing Institute and Inmarsat to analyse correlations within, and model demand for, their satellite connection data.

1.2 Data Overview

The data measure the satellite demand at different locations around the world summed at 5 minute intervals. We have 2 types of demand variables:

1. Forward demand volume - the amount of data sent from a ground station to users in response to user requests i.e. the volume of data served to users,
2. Return demand volume - the amount of data sent by users to a ground station i.e. the volume of data received from users.

These are the outcome data we wish to model.

Locations are described by a 3 character geohash, which represents a unique area on the surface of the globe. For each geohash, we have the above forward and return volume sums per every 5 minutes, but also broken down by class, and connection type. Classes are integer values that can be thought of as the type of device making the connection; they can be summarised broadly by as 'maritime', 'aeronautical', and 'land' connections. Connection type describes the type of data being requested, for example background or voice call.

Additionally we know the count - the number of unique users connected in that 5 minute period.

1.3 Main Objectives

- Determine how useful count data is in predicting forward and return volumes i.e. answer the question “Would it be worth modelling count data to help predict demand?”
- Produce models to predict the demand at the next step for a given geohash
- Explore the use of Convolutional Neural Networks to model the raw data

1.4 Approach

- We performed exploratory data analysis assessing spatial and temporal correlation of the demand, and clustering of geohashes.
- We treated the data as if it was tabular and modelled the relationship between features of geohashes (grouped by time, class, and connection type) and the demand.
- We treated the data as a 3D grid (a 2D grid where each pixel was the demand at one geohash, and time) and modelled this using a convolutional LSTM (ConvLSTM).
- We proposed theoretical models for time series modelling.

1.5 Main Conclusions

- Temporal autocorrelation is more significant than the spatial correlation.
- There is evidence the count variable is useful for predicting the demand in combination with other variables (see random forest *variable importance*).
- Our simple baseline of predicting the demand from the previous timestep performs well.

- A Random Forest with this information and instantaneous data (using no historical data) performs better.
- There's evidence that the ConvLSTM could perform well, but we need to run this model again on data grouped in the same way as the RF and Baseline to compare them.
- Time series, latent variable, and spatio-temporal models are worth exploring depending on the requirements of the model; specifically INLA (see Section 3.6)

1.6 Limitations

There was no access to code at the time of writing this report so implementation details are lacking. However, all results are reproducible with code referenced in this document. Implementation details are explicit within the code.

The data are quite sparse, with many geohashes returning near zero volume most of the time. This makes evaluation via mean squared error a little tricky, as those geohashes are not of greatest interest, but models predicting zero everywhere will perform relatively well by this metric. See Section 2.3.2 for an illustration of this issue.

There are some missing data i.e. for some geohash, class, connection type groups, data was not sampled at every 5 minute interval. This is problematic for time series modelling, and it must be decided how this should be treated. For tabular modelling, i.e. predicting the next forward or return volume for a given geohash, class, connection type group, we simply ignored these missing values. However, if comparing performance for different geohashes, classes, or connection types, we must note that this approach could bias results if the amount of data available is dramatically different.

Geohashes used are not equal in area, but the area is available as a derived variable. It's not clear how much of an issue that will be in reality.

To fit the ConvLSTM (and some other models) on the full data would have

required much more time/compute resources than we had available.

1.7 Recommendations for Future Work

Since they were not trained and evaluated on the same data, the baseline, Random Forest, and ConvLSTM should be rerun and compared more formally. We expect the ConvLSTM to outperform other methods given enough data and training time. We also only trained on the first week of data, so we have no view on potential seasonal change.

Since it is desired to predict demand further into the future, first establish the granularity required - how frequently to you intend to change the settings of the satellites? If the answer is 'only once per half an hour' the data can be aggregated up to that level and the models rerun. However, if more granularity is required *along with* a greater window of prediction (e.g. it's necessary to plan satellite changes every 5 minutes over the course of the next hour) we recommend exploring time series models.

Another recommendation is to construct a toy data generator. This could enable quicker and less restricted model comparison and testing. It has also been noted that your data is quite similar to rainfall data - this is publicly available and could serve useful to link to for future events.

2 Data Overview

2.1 Dataset Description

The data measure the satellite demand at different locations around the world summed at 5 minute intervals. We have 2 types of demand variables:

1. Forward demand volume - the amount of data sent from a ground station to users in response to user requests i.e. the volume of data served to users,
2. Return demand volume - the amount of data sent by users to a ground station i.e. the volume of data received from users.

These are the outcome data we wish to model.

Locations are described by a 3 character geohash, which represents a unique area on the surface of the globe. For each geohash, we have the above forward and return volume sums per every 5 minutes, but also broken down by class, and connection type. Classes are integer values that can be thought of as the type of device making the connection; they can be summarised broadly by as 'maritime', 'aeronautical', and 'land' connections. Connection type describes the type of data being requested, for example background or voice call.

Additionally we know the count - the number of unique users connected in that 5 minute period.

The data summed every 5 minutes is derived from individual data links between Inmarsat Ground Stations and User Terminals. Forward links are defined to be from an Inmarsat Ground Station to a User Terminal via a satellite. Return links are from a User Terminal back to a Ground Station via a satellite. The forward link volume and return link volumes may be correlated negatively or positively, significantly or insignificantly, depending on the application. For example, a phone call may have similar forward and return volumes when in use; however, this would not be true for a laptop downloading (but not uploading) data (referred to with connection type = 'background').

Volume is concentrated in a few areas (ports, major shipping routes, flight routes, etc.). As such the forecasting problem could be preceded by a feature extraction problem - such as clustering similar and/or nearby locations.

Data can be transferred for a number of reasons, such as users using the internet on a laptop; planes communicating with air traffic control or satellite phone users making a call. The user terminal class structure and connection type structure allows for these use cases to be separated to a large extent. As such different class/connection type combinations may require different methods/model calibrations.

There are 7402 unique geohashes and 25,200 unique time points recorded in the data. The total time span is 3 months (from 4th of July to 1st of October 2017). There are 12 unique values for user-end class and they are grouped into three categories, land, maritime and aeronautical. The forward and return volumes are pre-processed/normalised. The largest forward volume over the three months is 2577.4164 with standard deviation of 3.1127 and the largest return volume is 47.2006 with standard deviation of 0.9077. The data are quite large: the dimensionality of demand dataset is 91,701,707 rows 6 columns; the count dataset is 81,738,987 \times 4. Roughly approximating the data as being single 64 bit floats, this corresponds to about 5 Gigabytes, and 3 Gigabytes respectively (though in practice, reading the data in its entirety into memory using Python or R required $>$ 20GB).

2.1.1 Variable Names and Derived Data

N.B. The data derived from the raw data is shown indented underneath what it was derived from

- **time** – *datetime*: yyyy/mm/dd hh:mm:ss
 - hour – *int32*: summary of time
 - weekday – *int32*: summary of time
 - weekend – *int64*: summary of time
- **geohash** – *category*: 3 character hash value

- latitude – *float64*: lat in centre of geohash patch
- longitude – *float64*: long in centre of geohash patch
- **ueClass** – *int64*: The class of communication
 - ueCat – *category*: A summary of ueClass. One of ['maritime', 'aeronautical', 'land']
- **connectionType** – *int64*: The type of communication e.g. background or voice call
- **imsi_count** – *int64*: The count of connections in the patch
- **fwd_vol_sum** – *float64*: sum of the forward demand in the region
- **rtn_vol_sum** – *float64*: sum of the return demand in the region

2.2 Data Quality Issues

The data are quite sparse, with many geohashes returning near zero volume most of the time. This makes evaluation via mean squared error a little tricky, as those geohashes are not of greatest interest, but models predicting zero everywhere will perform relatively well by this metric. See Fig.8 for an illustration of this issue.

There are some missing data i.e. for some geohash, class, connection type groups, data was not sampled at every 5 minute interval. This is problematic for time series modelling, and it must be decided how this should be treated. For tabular modelling, i.e. predicting the next forward or return volume for a given geohash, class, connection type group, we simply ignored these missing values. However, if comparing performance for different geohashes, classes, or connection types, we must note that this approach could bias results if the amount of data available is dramatically different.

Geohashes used are not equal in area, but the area is available as a derived variable. It's not clear how much of an issue that will be in reality.

To fit the ConvLSTM (and some other models) on the full data would have required much more time/compute resources than we had available.

2.3 Exploratory Data Analysis

2.3.1 Univariate and Bivariate Analysis

N.B. The plots in this section are only for the first week of data. This was just in the interest of processing time. The scripts to preprocess the data and plots are available and were designed to require only configuration changes to run on the full data.

Fig.1 is a visualisation best viewed as an animated gif online. It gives a good overall view of what the data are.

Fig.2 and Fig.3 are histograms giving a picture what types of signals dominate the data. There is a bias to specific connection types, and classes. Indeed, the plot showing the imbalance between maritime, land, and aeronautical data provides some impetus to create separate models for them: if modelling the sum over classes, the model will likely predict land data poorly, since it makes up such a small proportion of the data.

Fig.4 and Fig.5 give the first hint that sparsity will likely cause issue: much of the outcome data is zero much of the time.

In Fig.6 we see that the relationship between the number of active terminals connected, and the forward and return volume of data is very noisy. However, it is certainly useful - there are few observations with many connected terminals and low data volume. In fact, in the analysis of the Random Forest later, there is evidence that this variable is indeed useful.

Figure 1: Demand over time: This figure is a snapshot of an animation that shows a plot of the forward volume over the first week every 15 minutes for each geohash. One dot represents one geohash. The volume has been normalized with larger values shown in as greener. In the animation, the shipping lines and flight paths can be seen clearly. We also see that many geohashes exhibit little variation. From the static image, we see there are many areas with no signal at all e.g. most of the landmass of Africa.

Figure 2: Connection Type: Connections are highly skewed to two specific types: 2 is 'background' data (normal internet connections)

Figure 3: Connection Class: Some classes dominate the data; On the left we see 6, 8 and 9 are most common. Each of these classes map one-to-one with a specific category: 'aeronautical', 'land', or 'maritime'. The distribution of the class summarised by category is shown on the right.

Figure 4: Count Data: The majority of count data values are either zero or one

Figure 5: Outcome data; the forward and return volume: These two plots are histograms. The volume of data sent to users is zero for the vast majority of geohas, class, connection type groups. The y axis shows the number of observations, the x axis shows the *square root* of the volume. This is to allow us to visualise the count all values, some are very large, whilst preserving zero data. Similarly, the volume of data received from users is largely zero. It follows a similar distribution but the values are an order of magnitude smaller than the forward volume.

Figure 6: Volume against count correlation: Whilst there is some correlation between count and forward/return volume, there are plenty of cases where low counts return high volumes (see the data points in the top left of each plot). However, high counts do more reliably return high volumes (there are fewer data points in the lower right of each plot). The colours blue, green, and red represent aeronautical, land, and maritime data respectively. *N.B. This only shows non-zero data.*

2.3.2 Sparsity

From Fig.5 we observed a very high volume of zero data. In Fig.7 we show which geohashes are responsible for this. This reveals flight paths, shipping routes, and the where the majority of the volume is served. In Fig.8 we aggregate the data and explore the volume served over time. From this we see the expected daily fluctuation, and also some potential data issues: there are gaps where no data is served, and a short period of approximately a week with a where missingness increases by about 5%.

Figure 7: Where is the sparsity?: This plot shows the proportion of timepoints at which each geohash served zero volume.

Figure 8: When is the sparsity?: This plot shows the proportion of zero or missing valued data over the first week. We see that there are certain time points which exhibit full zero data.

2.3.3 Spatial Clustering

In Fig.9 we show the result of a simple data aggregation followed by k-means clustering. The data is aggregated up to a geohash level and the mean and standard deviation ***across all time*** is calculated. These data are treated as 2D data points, and k-means clustering is used to split the data into five clusters.

Figure 9: Fitted clusters: The result of a k means clustering on the mean and standard deviation of each geohash. Note the hotpot corridor (seen as a red line) near Arabic countries, and low demand areas (seen in black).

3 Experiments and Results

3.1 Notation

In the following sections we use 'python like' notation, with indexes having an inclusive lower bound and exclusive upper bound. For example, $y[:t]$ is all values in the vector y up to but not including t , or $X[t+1:]$ is all observations in the matrix X , from and including index $t+1$ until the end.

3.2 Predicting the Next Demand Observation: Regression

The simplest model to begin with attempts merely to guess the next observation. We frame the problem as a regression: we can use all observed data to predict the next forward volume, or return volume at a given geohash (grouped by data class and connection type).

In this section, models are allowed to use:

- $X[t]$: the current observation data - all current information about location, signal type, and number of connections
- $X[:t]$: prior observation data
- $y[:t]$: prior outcome data - all previous demand observations

to achieve the modelling task of predicting the current outcome data $y[t]$.

They must avoid using any future information: $X[t+1:]$ and $y[t+1:]$. We make this explicit, as it is easy to do accidentally in the given data setting. For example, if using features that categorise a geohash based on the demand activity, the feature creation must not use the full dataset, only prior values the the desired time window of prediction.

3.3 Performance Metrics

In order to evaluate the success of our models we use the following two measures: R^2 and mean square error (MSE). They incorporate:

- y : true outcome values
- \hat{y} : predictions from the model
- \bar{y} : mean of the true outcomes

3.3.1 R^2

$$R^2(y, \hat{y}) = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{n_{samples}} (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^{n_{samples}} (y_i - \bar{y})^2}$$

3.3.2 MSE

$$MSE(y, \hat{y}) = \frac{1}{n_{samples}} \sum_{i=1}^{n_{samples}} (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2$$

3.3.3 Out-of-bag error

This is a method of splitting the data into a training and validation set for the purpose of estimating the generalisation error. Ensemble methods which use bootstrap aggregating to train each constituent model, such as the Random Forest, can calculate out-of-bag error, which is a (usually pessimistic) estimate for the generalisation error. In short, for each observation, the prediction is made using models in the ensemble which *did not use it for training*. The Random Forest model was assessed using this inbuilt validation method: the error metric was still MSE, but it was calculated on a different subset of data from the Baseline or the LSTM; this was not ideal, and done in the interest of time, and such that the model could train on all the maximum amount of data.

3.4 Evaluated Models

The following sections detail only models which were evaluated. More were proposed and explored, but no results were obtained before the deadline.

3.4.1 Naive Baseline

The most naive baseline is simply to assume outcomes are the same as they were observed at the previous time point: $y[t]=y[t-1]$.

Specifically, this calculation groups the outcome data by geohash, class, and connection type, and simply predicts the most recent observation prior to the current time.

*N.B. The implementation doesn't look for the volume specifically 5 minutes before, but instead the most recent **available** observation prior to the current time. If no prior observation is available, e.g. for the first time point, a prediction of 0 is made.*

In Fig.10 we explore lagging the baseline further back in time. This is a simple way of showing how autocorrelated the data are; it could also be used to inform what level of granularity should be used for future datasets.

The results are shown below in *Random Forest vs Baseline Results*.

3.4.2 Random Forest

Random forests work well out-of-the-box in a tabular data setting: they are able to model interactions in the data, and provide a very sensible method for assessing variable importance in this context. Given the time constraints, it was a sensible choice for a first model.

We fit two separate models which we denote RF1 and RF2. Comparison of these models illuminates the relative importance of the volume data 5 minutes ago, and the instantaneous data about a given geohash.

Figure 10: Baseline lag against R^2 : By increasing the lag, we can see how far back in time we can go before the prediction becomes as bad as simply predicting the mean value ($R^2 = 0$). The plot shows how the baseline performance decreases as the lag increases. For each value on the x axis, the model used to predict is $y[t] = y[t-\text{lag}]$. By about lag=15, i.e. predicting the current value as the same as 1.25 hours ago, the performance is about the same as predicting the mean value everywhere. Since this was fitted on a week of data, there are no values at 5×2016 minutes ago; this is predicting 0 everywhere, which is worse than predicting the mean i.e. ($R^2 < 0$).

For RF1 we first model only instantaneous data i.e. we ignore the previous volume reading and see how well we can perform using only information about the geohash.

For RF2 we do as before but additionally provide the previous (forward *and* return) volume reading. The performance dramatically improves, and, though dramatically less important, the instantaneous data about the geohash is still used.

RF1: input $X[t]$

Does not perform as well as baseline which suggests that instantaneous data is not as important as the prior outcome data. This is explored in RF2 below.

RF2: input $(X[t], y[t-1])$

Since RF1 was outperformed by the baseline, we supply the model with the previous outcome data in addition to the instantaneous observation data.

Random Forest vs Baseline Results

	RF1	RF2	Baseline
r2	0.514	0.753	0.637
mse	4.401	2.235	3.479

Table 1: Forward volume results

	RF1	RF2	Baseline
r2	0.441	0.693	0.573
mse	0.475	0.260	0.374

Table 2: Return volume results

Variable Importance

Relative importance calculated using the Mean Decrease Gini metric - as discussed in Han 2016, this is not affected in the same way as a permutation importance method with respect to correlated input variables. In this way, we can also use the Random Forest to assess the importance of variables whilst incorporating the fact they may be correlated.

In Fig.11 and Fig.12, we show the relative importance plots resulting from the fitted models. Contrasting the figures, we see that the new data (i.e.

the forward and return volume 5 minutes before, the bars on the far right) are very important to RF2. This this variable will be near the top of most trees. Note that, from these plots, we can also conclude that the count is indeed useful for prediction, even in the presence of the previous volume.

Next steps for the Random Forest model

The logical extension to this modelling process is to also provide historical observation data $X[:t]$, and increase the amount of prior outcome data available to the model e.g. the previous hour $y[t-12:t]$.

Next, provide data about the neighbouring geohashes, then their neighbours.

Finally, note that individual trees are very interpretable - the importance plots in Fig.12 suggests that the Random Forest may be overpowered. analysis). In this data setting, first, fit a simple linear regression model with forward and return volume 5 minutes ago, and the count data and compare the performance. On the same data, fit a simple tree with a small maximum depth.

3.4.3 ConvLSTM

N.B. For this experiment, data was grouped by geohash alone i.e. the outcome data from all class x type combinations was summed for every geohash. This was done to simplify the data for an initial experiment.

The Convolutional LSTM models the data as a 128 x 256 dimensional matrix for every time point. Given the spatial nature of the data, this is probably much more appropriate than modelling in a tabular fashion and feature engineering. Given what can be seen from Fig.1, the tabular data would have to summarise statistics about all neighbouring geohashes (at least) to model the moving ships and planes. Combining convolutional patches and a temporal model, the ConvLSTM is able to capture these statistics.

Another benefit of using a ConvLSTM is scalability - these models can be trained on batches of data in an online fashion, so data can grow very

Figure 11: RF1 relative importance: The variable importance for RF1 predicting the forward, and return demand respectively. They are very similar.

Figure 12: RF2 relative importance: The variable importance for RF2 predicting the forward, and return demand respectively. We see that the new data are by far the most important.

large and open source frameworks can easily handle this.

For more information about ConvLSTMs, see Xingjian 2015. The authors focus on precipitation ‘nowcasting’ which is a very similar data domain to our problem. We use a very similar but slightly simplified architecture and training regime, roughly:

- ConvLSTM with 30 x 33 kernels and a ReLU activation function;
- Batch Normalisation;
- 3D Convolutional Layer using a kernel size 333 with output size of 1, and a ReLU activation function;
- All weights were initialised using He Normal initialisation (see He 2015);
- Adam optimiser with learning rate and decay of 10^{-4} and 10^{-6} respectively

We also tried using larger kernel sizes or stacking ConvLSTM as recommended in Xingjian 2015 but they did not yield any substantial improvement.

Results

We initially summed the data up to the level of 1 hour, then increased the granularity up to 30 minutes, then 5 minutes. Additionally, we calculated the mse on only those geohashes that exhibited at least one non-zero value in the period.

	60 mins	30 mins	5 mins
mse	0.32	0.28	0.15
mse (non-zero data)	7.71	6.90	3.16

These results are very promising and show that the network has learned something. The comparison with the evaluation on non-zero data also shows that the model is suffering from the sparse data somewhat (it is a reasonably good strategy to predict zero everywhere). We only had enough time to get to about 30 epochs training on the first week of data;

the error curve was very much still on its way down. Given more training time and data, this could well prove to be a promising method.

Improvements

Some ideas for immediate improvements:

- Tweak the lookback parameter to capture faster movements like air transport;
- Implement a more complete model as in the original paper - including a stack of ConvLSTM (encode first, then predict);
- Normalisation of data could improve drastically the training time as in Xingjian 2015
- Add other variables in each cell/geohash within the maps (connection type, etc);
- Using so-called Image Data Generator to construct the batches inline instead of having static dataset which requires huge amount of memory to be stored;
- Plot the convolutional kernels; do they look like sensible components that could generate the data?

3.5 Issues to note

There are a few issues to make clear:

1. **We can't compare models without rerunning baseline + RF, or ConvLSTM because they were trained on very different data.** This was because different people were running the different models. It was decided that the Neural Network model should be trained on data summed up to the geohash level in the interest of time; this only became apparent to the analysts working on the baseline and Random Forest at a stage too late to recalculate. The baseline and RF are modelling data grouped by geohash, class, and connection type, whereas the ConvLSTM models data grouped

only by geohash (i.e. the sum over all classes and connection types). This makes the error artificially low!

2. The comparison between the random forest and the baseline is not like-for-like: the model is evaluated with the built-in out-of-bag error. This was just in the interest of time and really we should conduct a train/test split for all models to compare.
3. We modelled using features obtained from the clustering process - **this encodes future information**, therefore results will be slightly optimistic. Indeed, we see that the standard deviation of the volume at the geohash is an important feature. If the standard deviation were to change over (long term) time, this is not an easy feature to use

3.6 Conclusions

From the Random Forest experiments we see that the baseline of predicting the same demand as 5 minutes ago is hard to beat, but can be surmounted by including information about the geohash.

The ConvLSTM has shown some promising initial results. To conclude about its effectiveness, the experiment must be run again on the same data as the baseline. This can be achieved easily by running the referenced code.

However, both of these models are limited. They are optimised to predict only the next step. Thus, if the interest is in demand at greater time intervals in the future, they may not be appropriate. They can both be used to predict arbitrarily far into the future, but errors will increase. This is because, to do make predictions further than 5 minutes ahead, they must predict using their previous predictions as input, and therefore errors will add up.

A solution to this would be to model multiple steps forward and penalise accordingly, or model the data explicitly as a time series.

3.6.1 Other methods explored

The following methods were detailed in the preliminary report, but no results obtained. More information can be provided upon request.

- Latent variable modelling
- Vector Autoregressive Process; see Hamilton 1994 and Lutkepohl 2005
- Dynamic Linear Models (in combination with PCA)
- Particle Filters, Partially Observed Markov Processes (POMPs); see King 2016 and Pfeifer 1981
- Zero-inflated/hurdle spatio-temporal models, **specifically INLA (Lindgren 2015)**; see Hu 2011, Cameron 2008, Fernandes 2009, Zeileis 2008

4 Future Work

We recommend two initial first steps:

1. Re-run the ConvLSTM and the Baseline code on the full dataset and at the same level of aggregation
2. Formulate a harder problem, such as predict 30 minutes into the future, and compare the ConvLSTM to a time series method
 - a. This method could be evaluated by requesting a prediction for every 5 minutes in the following 30 (i.e. a vector of size 6), and the squared error taken across this period

A poisson process could be used to predict the count (or volume by use of binning) at a given time, X_t , at a time t , solving for some diffusion rate $r(x, t)$ using an algorithm such as the Integrated Nested Laplace Approximation (INLA - see Lindgren 2015). This has been applied to rainfall data with success. As noted above, this is very similar to your data.

A second approach could be proceed with feature engineering and attempt to capture neighbouring geohash information with statistics e.g. does it look like an aeroplane/boat is about to pass through me? If so, what's its current demand.

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A Team Members

- Jessie Liu

Jessie is an enrichment student at the Alan Turing Institute. Her research is to use statistical methods and machine learning techniques to analyse neuroimaging data and behavioural data. She was the facilitator of the group, mainly coordinating the project. She also contributed to some structure exploration, report writing and presentation making.

- Soudeep Deb

Soudeep is a Ph.D. Candidate at the Department of Statistics, University of Chicago. His research interests are time series data, spatial statistics, spatio-temporal modelling and application of statistics in sports research. Soudeep contributed to this report in exploratory data analysis (sparsity, spatial and temporal correlation) and in discussing VAR model and hurdle spatio-temporal model. Besides statistics, he is passionate about football, photography and blogging.

- James Owers

Music generation, neural networks, random forests, data analysis

James is a 2nd year PhD @ University of Edinburgh working on music generation at a signal level, and at a MIDI level.

On this project, his contributions were: Data Description & Visualisation, Modelling data definitions, The Baseline, The Random Forest, and writing up the report.

- Giovanni Mizzi

Giovanni is a PhD student in the Mathematics for Real-World Systems Doctoral Training Centre at the University of Warwick.

His research focuses on using online data from Google Trends and Twitter to improve estimates of dengue incidence in Brazil based on delayed official data.

His focus is on operationally realistic models that could be used in practice.

He contributed on this project in exploratory data analysis looking at sparsity. spatial and temporal correlation visualisations.

- Oluwole K. Oyebamiji

Oluwole Oyebamiji is currently a senior research associate in the Department of Mathematics and Statistics at Lancaster University, UK. He received his PhD in Statistical modelling from The Open University, UK in 2014. His research interests include Bayesian methods, multivariate analysis, experimental design, statistical modelling and big data analytics. Oluwole contributed to this report by combining the mixture of PCA and dynamic linear models for modelling the datasets.

- Valentin Courgeau

MRes/PhD student at Imperial College London, Mathematics/Statistics. Currently undertaking an MRes in Financial Computing at Imperial College/UCL as first year of PhD on Multivariate Extreme Value Theory with applications on renewable energy markets / green finance. For this project, I worked on implementing a deep learning structure using ConvLSTM-CNN to perform sequence prediction on maps of geohashes. This included creating datasets, data transformation into small collection of geohash maps as well as full end-to-end implementation of training procedure given a dataset using Keras.

- Rui Xin Lee

(PhD, Statistics Department, Warwick University). Practicing Data Scientist in the automotive industry. In this project I worked on EDA including producing an animation to visualise demand changes in each geolocation over time, producing a variogram to describe spatial continuity of data, clustering geohashes according to their aggregated demand and terminal count statistical properties, created features and implemented a kNN model to predicted 5 minute interval demand on all geohashes.

- Virginia Rutten

Virginia is a joint PhD student between the Gatsby Computational Neuroscience Unit at University College London in the Sahani Lab and the Ahrens Lab at the HHMI Janelia Research Campus.

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